

**PROBLEMS OF PERCEPTION AND UNDERSTANDING OF THE TEXT
(PSYCHOLINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF THE SEMANTICS OF THE
NOMINATIVE UNITS OF THE TEXT)**

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Annotation: The psycholinguistic approach to the text is one of the most actual issues in modern times. The article examines the psycholinguistic features of the literary text in compared languages. Acceptance, understanding and perception of the literary text is the basis of psycholinguistic analysis.

Keywords: psycholinguistic research, literary text, discourse, partition, understanding.

INTRODUCTION

A literary text is a sample of language which can be read and understood.

Psycholinguists consider it necessary to talk about the unity of the processes of perception and understanding in a text wherein the verbal reasoning memory represents an etalon (sounds, word-group, word) system hierarchy. On the sensing level, the word is the etalon, while the sensing is executed based on the object-system code, formed in the process of understanding. The object-system code, on the one hand, gives meaning to work's material elements (separate words, facts, phenomena used by the author), while on the other hand, it itself constantly changes, clarified and specified, influenced by this material [4, p.4].

In understanding the text additional factors also influence on the reader as, general knowledge, episodic expectations, associated relations, cultural awareness, and world-view.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Y.V. Aliyev speaking about the structure of the literary text, notes that it combines two main components. These are the information and the expression of the component of information. "Informative structure forms the basis of the text of a poem or prose. A language unit with any text or syntactic boundaries is impossible without information. The scarcity or abundance of information leads to the emergence of the most diverse language units (a word combination, a simple sentence, a compound sentence, a mixed compound sentence, a complex syntactic whole) from incomplete syntax to complete syntax. That is, the volume of information determines the structural complexity of the syntactic unit " [2, p.178]. The study of deep layers of the text, which are not observed at first glance, but only as a result of a thorough analysis, makes it necessary to consider a number of points, as well as the category of partition. "Partition a structural-semantic category that ensures the completeness and the connection of the units belonging to different language levels in the literary text" [5, p.226].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the course of the dialogue, we see that friends have already forgiven each other. The friend who first tried the conversation says:

- Go to the block number nine on Nardaransky Street. There are two rooms on the second floor, like a decorated bride! Everything is in it, in private hands, the owner sells it. And for the price of water: you will get five or six thousand. Don't stop! [8, p.228].

Let's pay attention to the continuation of the dialogue.

I was shaking my friend's hand and running. I found that house. The owner of the room had not yet slept. He sat sadly, as if waiting for me.

- Hello!

- Hello!

- The seller of the room is here

I finish my question; happily replied:

- Of course. My nephew, tell me if you want to look at it or buy? [8, p.229].

As can be seen from the dialogue, a third person enters the conversation - the seller of the house. The ethnic group of the host, his emotions, his inner world are expressed in one or two sentences.

The omission or addition of any component during communication, the repetition of the same words indicates the psychological state of the speaker. The modality and intonation of the sentences also indicate the emotional state of the speaker.

Continuation of the dialogue:

He took my hand in the palm of his hand, which was as big and thick as a sledge, and leaned towards me, saying firmly:

- Will you get it?

- I'll take it!

- Shall I say a word?

- Say a word!

- In a word, I see that you are a good boy. You have a good job, one word:

I will give you these rooms for a few, five thousand manats.

- Five thousand manats?

- Yes!

- I got it!

- I sold it! God bless you!

- Bye!

A.Mammadov emphasizing the role of formal means of communication in the formation of the text, including phonetic (alliteration, assonance); morphological (repetition of gender, time, case category features); lexical (complete, incomplete, i.e. zero repetition of words in different grammatical forms); syntactic repetition (complete and incomplete repetition of word order, chiasm, etc.); lexico-

grammatical means (lexical relevance, connectors, prepositions, determinants, etc.); includes deictic elements (different types of pronouns, adverbs, tense forms of the verbs, articles, etc.) [7, p.54].

In a normal person, texting habits are so automated that there may be no transitions between thought and text, and the main form of live communication is spontaneous text.

CONCLUSION

There are 4 types of text modules: 1. Nominative component in the creation of the text, 2. synthetic and transcendental component, 3. grammar, morphology, 4. sounding of the text.

Among these components, the semantic- pragmatic component plays an important role, and the achieved set of goal is aimed in the interaction between them.

The process of influencing the reader can be carried out with the help of conceptual and linguistic means: conceptual means are based on the meaning behind verbal cues, reader's mind, language, semantic versatility of the text, actualization of hidden meanings, new worldview and evaluation of reproduction means creating a semantic increase.

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